

EXCELERATE Deliverable D1.7

Project Title:	ELIXIR-EXCELERATE: Fast-track ELIXIR implementation and drive early user exploitation across the life sciences	
Project Acronym:	ELIXIR-EXCELERATE	
Grant agreement no.:	676559	
	H2020-INFRADEV-2014-2015/H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1	
Deliverable title:	Description of the registry user helpdesk & impact on user support via community forums	
WP No.	WP1	
Lead Beneficiary:	38 - DTU	
WP Title	Tools Interoperability and Service Registry	
Contractual delivery date:	30 September 2018	
Actual delivery date:	09 October 2018	
WP leader:	Søren Brunak and Alfonso Valencia	38 - DTU; 12 - BSC
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1. Executive Summary

The objective of EXCELERATE Deliverable 1.7 is to provide comprehensive support for users of the ELIXIR Tools and Data Services Registry (<https://bio.tools>). The core aim is to deliver impact for end-users broadly, making it easier for them to contribute to and use bio.tools. Users are of three types: *tool providers* such as major institutional providers and community-driven collections, *tool developers* including developers of individual tools, workflows and workbench environments, and *tool users* including scientists and bioinformaticians. We originally anticipated to provide direct support to *tool users*, primarily by leveraging the existing and highly popular user bioinformatics forums (BioStars, BioPlanet etc.) This remains a good objective (highlighted in the EXCELERATE midterm review) but is not yet timely, as it cannot be done in an impactful way given the resources available to EXCELERATE and sheer number of tool users.

Instead, we have focused efforts on documentation and targeted community support, which more directly address current needs. This report describes work done with ELIXIR-EXCELERATE resources:

- comprehensive *documentation* including
 - **Curators Guide** including general considerations, EDAM ontology annotations, and specific guidelines for individual software attributes and types of tool defined in biotoolsSchema 3.0.0 and used in the Tool Information Standard
 - **EDAM Guidelines** including an *Editors Guide* of general best practice for technical and scientific development of EDAM, and a *Developers Guide* to the technical processes
 - **technical documentation** for biotoolsSchema, EDAM and the bio.tools API
 - **project documentation** including aims, scope, design principles, contribution mechanisms, events, governance *etc.*
 - **bio.tools User Guide** (emerging) to help users with practical use of the bio.tools interfaces
- focussed *community support* including:
 - supporting an emerging network of bio.tools **Thematic Editors** (highlighted in EXCELERATE midterm review) including an illustration (as a publication in preparation, summarised in D1.8) of how Editors oversee coverage and quality of bio.tools and EDAM in specific thematic areas (national and scientific). Editors are assisted by student helpers supported by the ELIXIR DK **bio.tools studentship scheme**
 - collaboration with **proteomics community** working towards comprehensive coverage and high quality annotation of proteomics analysis tools, and applications to workflow composition. An article “*Automated workflow composition in mass spectrometry based proteomics*” has been accepted for publication in *Bioinformatics*¹ (summarised in D1.8)
 - collaboration with **Euro/Global-bioimaging** via the NEUBIAS Cost Action, for the curation of bioimage analysis tools, developing EDAM-Bioimaging ontology for this purpose and aligning the schema/content of bio.tools and Bio Image Information Index (<https://biii.eu>) with view to future surfacing in bio.tools of this content
 - collaboration with technical communities, including **Galaxy, Common Workflow Language Communities** and **Biocontainers** towards the crosslinking and interoperability of these resources with bio.tools
- general *end-user support*
 - via **GitHub**: 832 issues tracked (613 closed, 219 open) within bio.tools, biotoolsSchema and EDAM trackers
 - via registry-support mailing list, community mailing lists and at 10 events

The work addresses specific developments as envisioned for milestones below (all due in M36):

- M1.5 “Good Practice Guidelines”
- M1.6 “Implementation of resource metadata catalogue & evaluation of impact of Resource Synergy Meeting series”

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty646>

Work in ongoing in all areas to deliver impact for end-users broadly, making it easier for them to contribute to and use bio.tools. The report summarises progress made and anticipated developments.

2. Impact

We have delivered impact to scientific communities that are using tools, with concrete outcomes in particular for the proteomics and bioimaging communities. We have delivered comprehensive and high quality guidelines, and responsive support via GitHub primarily, that underpin the sustainable use of the infrastructure in the long-term.

3. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver a discovery portal built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key resources for bioinformatics resources world-wide.	x	
2	Service monitoring, resource integration, interoperability aspects, and community centred benchmarking efforts.		x
3	Deliver impact for end-users across academia, health organizations, and industry.	x	

4. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: • Yes • No

5. Adjustments made

The deliverable is only slightly delayed due to the drafting of the final report.

6. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	1	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Tools Interoperability and Service Registry		
Lead	Søren Brunak (DK) and Alfonso Valencia (ES)		
<p>Participant number and person months per participant</p> <p>1 – EMBL 12.00; 2 – UOXF 6.00; 5 – UTARTU 43.00; 10 - IRB 13.00; 12 - BSC 11.00; 17 - INESC-ID 1.24; 21 – UiB 18.00; 25 – SIB 9.50; 26 – CNRS 9.00; 29 – IP 12.00; 35 – MU 18.20; 38 - DTU 26.00 (LTPs: UCPH 25.00 + AU 25.00)</p>			
<p>Objectives</p> <p>WP1 will deliver a discovery portal built upon a federated curation of a wide range of key resources for bioinformatics resources world-wide.</p> <p>It will involve service monitoring, resource integration, interoperability aspects, and community centred benchmarking efforts. All activities, including intensive user support, are focused around delivering impact for end-users across academia, health organizations, and industry. The ELIXIR Tools and Data Services Registry is the cornerstone of the WP.</p> <p>Work Package Leads: Søren Brunak (DK) and Alfonso Valencia (ES)</p>			
<p>Description of work and role of partners</p> <p>WP1 - Tools Interoperability and Service Registry [Months: 1-48]</p> <p>DTU, EMBL, UOXF, UTARTU, IRB, BSC, INESC-ID, UiB, SIB, CNRS, IP, MU</p> <p>Based on its first release in January 2015, WP1 will further develop the ELIXIR registry mechanism, interfaces and content upkeep strategy. The WP contains plans for the development and extension of its functionality and scope (Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.5). The federated curation of the registry will ensure comprehensive content and high quality annotations, both of which are essential for the sustainable impact of the registry in the community. Scientific and technical consistency and utility will be achieved by using the EDAM controlled vocabulary. Exposing the results of efforts addressing tool benchmarking and monitoring of the resources listed in the registry will provide the end-user with a robust, scientifically relevant measure of tool quality and performance. Furthermore, the work on workbench integration and interoperability will lower the cost to developers of integrating their resources in key workflow environments, and assist the users with establishing and updating their day-to-day workflows. Finally, WP1 contains plans for comprehensive, registry related user support, which will ensure impact for users, and a dynamic management element, including marketing and community development to build the federated organization behind the registry.</p> <p>The user-centric approach will thus stand as the guiding principle for the entire portal and guard its relevance to the community.</p>			

Task 1.1: Federated Registry Curation (96PM)

This task will deliver essential scientific and technical coverage in the registry and the vocabulary (EDAM) that underpins registry consistency and utility. A major community curation effort is required, including vocabulary development, resource annotation and registration. To ensure that the curation is high quality and sustainable, it must be federated across registry stakeholders, hence a major priority is building and supporting the community of federated curators. In tandem, the curation will be accompanied by focused software and other technical developments, that automate, validate and embed the curation process in relevant software systems; the essential underpinning of sustainability.

The registry has two primary purposes; to help discover tools and services and use them. Discovery means to find, understand, compare and select. It is a prerequisite to (inter)operability, which demands a precise understanding of software dependencies. Our approach is based on the acceptance that software interoperability will, for the foreseeable future, be implemented primarily by developers rather than intelligent software agents. We will therefore, once a comprehensive set of ELIXIR Node resources are described in basic detail, extend the curation of the registry to annotate, using EDAM Format URIs (unified resource identifiers), the data formats that are supported by tools and data services.

From this, we will analyse the format-usage landscape to provide a basis for targeted software developments to improve interoperability of registered resources. We foresee these developments, which might include conversion of tools to use common formats, and development of format- converter software where needed, to be facilitated via the Matchmaking Service mechanism (D1.5).

The registry scope will be:

1. Comprehensive coverage of ELIXIR Node resources, including tools, data services (APIs) and host databases, prioritising ELIXIR-badged services and new resources from the Use Cases.
2. Coverage of other biomedical science Research Infrastructures (RIs), and key resources beyond ELIXIR (European and non-European).

A task force will be comprised of ontology developers, curators, scientific domain experts and relevant technical experts. It will run Curation and Usability hackathons with the recurrent theme of curation: resource annotation and registration, with necessary EDAM development. To facilitate networking and community build-up, two types of social event will be combined with the hackathons:

1. Knowledge Exchange Workshops, including representatives of relevant infrastructures, institutes and projects, on themes related to the registry suggested by the community.
2. Cross-domain Strategy Workshops to gather technical officers from ELIXIR Nodes, RIs, key resources, and other key initiatives, to discuss and develop common approaches for registry curation across RIs internationally.

EDAM provides the registry with a consistent vocabulary for topics (general scientific and technical disciplines), operations (tool functions), types of data, and specific data formats and data identifiers. Task 1.1 will work with the existing EDAM community, develop its open governance and contribution mechanisms and deliver essential utilities to ensure that maintenance, validation and community development is

sustainable in the long term. We will assess and validate coverage by correlating EDAM concepts to terms used for curation, which will then inform and drive necessary additions and desirable clean-ups (removal of concepts). We will develop focused essential utilities for EDAM maintenance including automation of the release process, basic validation of content, reporting of changes between versions, deployment to ontology browsers such as BioPortal and OLS, technical integration of EDAM with applications including the registry and others, mapping of provider-supplied terms and phrases to EDAM, and revise annotation

upon new EDAM releases.

To underpin the sustainability of the federated curation, this task will deliver focused software and other technical developments that will automate the registration and update of provider-supplied information, leveraging their own local software infrastructure where possible. We will work with providers to support them in doing this, and, where possible, adapt technically the local solutions to make them more broadly applicable to others. Further, in order to facilitate coverage, all relevant resource providers will be given smooth and convenient access to resource registration. This will be achieved by a combination of simple-to-obtain local login accounts and opening for using eduGAIN authentication to register resources.

Finally, this task will ensure that registered resource are citable, discoverable by the major search engines, and are placed in scientific context. It will also include technical mark-up to support “Semantic Web” applications, e.g. Schema.org-compatible microdata or RDFa to support Google “rich snippets” and other structured search results in the major browsers. Hence, the registry will promote the registered resources and deliver impact for developers and institutes by making resources rank higher in search results and hence more findable.

Task 1.1 partners: DK, NO, FR, CH, CZ, EMBL-EBI, PT

Task 1.2: Benchmarking and Monitoring (15PM)

This task will support the monitoring and community benchmarking of analytical tools, in a systematic and sustainable way e.g. based on the efforts in WP2. Firstly, it will review the existing service quality and performance metrics and assess their usefulness in the context of a registry. This may require development of a light-weight controlled vocabulary capturing the concepts distilled from the preparatory activities above and those of WP2.

Task 1.2 partners: DK, ES, CZ, CH

Task 1.3: Workbench integration and interoperability (36PM)

There is general trend towards the use of workflows as a preferred environment for the convenient use of tools and data access, especially when resources must be used in combination with one another. This task will boost convenience and resource interoperability by implementing a Workbench Integration Enabler service that will develop the vision “register your software once - get it supported everywhere”. Technically, this service will translate the description of any tool or service that is registered in the Tools and Data Services Registry into the metadata format required by the existing major workbenches, including Moby, Galaxy and Taverna. Furthermore, we will develop a new, lightweight Service Launchpad for running tools and services

which have programmatic access and which can be invoked using information available in the registry.

To develop the Enabler Service, we will align the registry software description model and the schemas used by the workbench systems or required by the Launchpad, and subsequently revise the model and schemas to facilitate the metadata transfer. Furthermore, to prove the principle, new high priority tools and services, including those developed in the Use Cases.

Task 1.3 partners: DK, EE, FR, CH, PT

Task 1.4: User support and derived registry development (36.7PM)

This task will provide direct and indirect user support to deliver impact for ELIXIR end-users. Direct support will be achieved primarily by leveraging the existing and highly popular user bioinformatics forums (BioStars, BioPlanet etc.).

A User-support specialist will patrol such forums and respond to questions in one of four ways:

- 1) Where resources answering to the Users needs exist in the registry, a link to them in the registry will be provided via our API.
- 2) Where resources exist in the registry, but the registry API cannot be used to answer the question directly, they will request new features of the API and in so doing drive development of the Query Interface.
- 3) Where an appropriate resource exists but has not been registered, they will request the appropriate registry curator add it to the registry.
- 4) Where a registered resource exists that is close, but not quite what is required, they will forward feature requests to the appropriate developers, possibly via the Matchmaking Service (D1.5).

Indirect user support will be achieved primarily by ensuring the registry interfaces are highly usable and match very closely the needs of the user. To achieve this, we will run user experience sessions during the Curation and Usability community. Scientific and technical consistency and utility will be achieved by using the EDAM controlled vocabulary.

Exposing the results of efforts addressing tool benchmarking and monitoring of the resources listed in the registry will provide the end-user with a robust, scientifically relevant measure of tool quality and performance. Furthermore, the hackathons (see Task 1.1) in order to evaluate usability. We will develop comprehensive Good Practice Guidelines for the curation of the registry in all aspects, but in particular the annotation of common types of resources using EDAM.

We will also participate in the development of an ELIXIR Experts Registry where users can discover relevant expertise within the ELIXIR network, and an ELIXIR User Helpdesk to answer general questions concerning use of the registry, forwarding specialised scientific and technical enquiries to relevant experts.

Task 1.4 partners: DK, CH

Task 1.5: Management, marketing and community build-up (46PM)

This task will build the federated organisation primarily by identifying and facilitating key collaborations between registry stakeholders. This will be achieved by organising

'Resource Synergy Meetings', where we will identify and encourage targeted software developments, e.g. to coordinate curation and data sharing. We will also promote resource integration and usability, e.g. by cross-linking resources and through API harmonization. As a prerequisite to these Synergy Meetings, a Resource Metadata Catalogue, listing all relevant resources, their scientific and technical scope, and information fields (schema), will be compiled and used to compare providers and identify redundancies. We will also use these meeting to cross-link the Tools & Data Services Registry with other key ELIXIR registries, for example the Training Materials Registry, the ELIXIR Events Registry, and the Experts Registry.

This task will also develop an oversight and management strategy and leverage partners within and beyond the ELIXIR organisation to implement strategy. To drive delivery, it will identify and encourage collaboration, monitor actions, identify delays, and intervene where necessary. It will raise community awareness and therefore impact by contributing to a forceful marketing campaign via all appropriate marketing channels, including popular social media. It will provide support to funders, publishers and others at the EU and national level, that policy is aligned with the aims of the registry organisation.

Task 1.5 partners: DK

7. Appendix 1: Description of the registry user helpdesk & impact on user support via community forums

1. Technical overview

User support has been squarely focused on supporting communities and end-users of various types (Figure 1) to contribute to the development of technical components and drive content quality improvement in the registry. The priority has been on *tool providers* including major institutional providers and other software collections but is shifting more towards *tool developers* and ultimately must focus squarely on *tool users*, supporting them with discovery and interoperability of tools.

Figure 1. Supporting bio.tools users to drive content improvement

In this deliverable report we summarise developments only. Further information is available online. The work done includes documentation, focused support for scientific and technical communities and end-user support (primarily via GitHub).

Documentation (Section 8.2) includes general project and technical information as well as specific guidelines or technical references (sub-bullets below):

- **bio.tools docs** (Section 8.2.1) including:
 - **Curators Guide**
 - **bio.tools API reference**
 - **bio.tools attribute model**
 - **bio.tools User Guide** (work in progress)
 - **bio.tools Editors Guide** (work in progress)
- **biotoolsSchema docs** (Section 8.2.2) including:
 - **online technical specification**
- **EDAM docs** (Section 8.2.3) including:
 - **EDAM Editors Guide**
 - **EDAM Developers Guide**
- **Tool Information Standard** (Section 8.2.3, described in D1.5)

End-user support in context of the bio.tools community build-up process (Section 8.3) includes:

- via **GitHub**: within bio.tools, biotoolsSchema, EDAM and other trackers
- via **sifterapp**
- via registry-support mailing list, community mailing lists and at 10 events

1.1 Milestone M1.5 (“Good practice guidelines”)

The developments address completely this milestone: we have developed Good Practice Guidelines for the bio.tools project broadly.

1.2 Milestone M1.6 (“Implementation of resource metadata catalogue & evaluation of impact of Resource Synergy Meeting series”)

M1.6 as envisioned in the EXCELERATE proposal would compile a Resource Metadata Catalogue of potential sources of bio.tools content, including their scientific and technical scope and information fields (schema). Further, “Synergy meetings” would help build the federated organisation by enabling collaborations between registry stakeholders and encourage targeted developments, e.g. for curation and data sharing. We already described (in D1.2) the major tool collections covered by bio.tools and how import/coverage is being accomplished following a process of schema mapping, entry mapping, transformation etc. and (in D1.1 and D1.2) an extensive program of events to these ends. In D1.3 report, we describe how we have taken the metadata catalogue idea much further, by providing a novel graphical user interface for browsing resources based on their scientific annotation.

Below, we highlight additional developments of relevance to M1.6 including *focused community support*:

- collaboration with **proteomics community** (Section 8.4.1) working towards comprehensive coverage and high quality annotation of proteomics analysis tools, and applications to workflow composition. An article “*Automated workflow composition in mass spectrometry based proteomics*” has been accepted for publication in *Bioinformatics*² (described in D1.8)
- collaboration with **Euro/Global-bioimaging** (Section 8.4.2) via the NEUBIAS Cost Action, for the curation of bioimage analysis tools, developing EDAM-Bioimaging ontology for this purpose and aligning the schema/content of bio.tools and Bio Image Information Index (<https://biii.eu>) with view to future surfacing in bio.tools of this content
- collaboration with technical communities (Section 8.4.3), including **Galaxy**, **Common Workflow Language Communities** and **Biocontainers**, towards the integration and interoperability of bio.tools with the broader resource landscape
- supporting an emerging network of bio.tools **Thematic Editors** (Section 8.3.1) - highlighted in EXCELERATE midterm review - including an illustration (as a publication in preparation) of how Editors oversee coverage and quality of bio.tools and EDAM in specific thematic areas (national and scientific)
- A comprehensive list of additional sources of content, to be covered in due course was catalogued
<https://biotools.sifterapp.com/projects/39503/issues>

2. Documentation

All documentation is available online (Table 1) and is crosslinked to ensure ease of navigation; this was done systematically (*i.e.* for all information fields) for the Curators Guide, biotoolSchema technical documentation and bio.tools attribute model. The documentation was developed to a rigorous standard, all guidelines use the key words

² <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv646>

“MUST”, “MUST NOT” *etc.* as described in RFC 2119³. The documentation is maintained in GitHub (Table 2) and is open to community contributions and improvements.

Documentation	Link
bio.tools docs (general)	biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest
Curators Guide	biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/curators_guide.html
bio.tools API reference	https://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api_reference_dev.html
bio.tools API usage guide	https://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api_usage_guide_dev.html
bio.tools User Guide (work in progress)	biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/user_guide.html
bio.tools Editors Guide (work in progress)	biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/editors_guide.html
biotoolsSchema docs (general)	biotoolsschema.readthedocs.io/en/latest
biotoolsSchema docs (technical specification)	bio-tools.github.io/biotoolsSchema/
EDAM docs (general)	edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/
EDAM Editors Guide	edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/editors_guide.html
EDAM Developers Guide	edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/developers_guide.html
Tool Information Standard	bio-tools.github.io/Tool-Information-Standard

Table 1. Documentation for the technical components.

Repository	Link
bio.tools docs	github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsdocs
biotoolsSchema docs	github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsschemadocs/
EDAM ontology docs	github.com/edamontology/edamontologydocs
Tool Information Standard docs	github.com/bio-tools/tool-Information-Standard

Table 2. Repositories where documentation for the technical components is maintained.

2.1 bio.tools documentation

bio.tools docs include aims, scope, contribution mechanisms, events, governance *etc.* In addition:

³ <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc2119.txt>

- **Curators Guide** cover software attributes and types of tool defined in biotoolsSchema 3.0.0 and used in the Tool Information Standard
 - **general guidelines** to be considered *before* creating a bio.tools entry, including how best to model tool functions in their complexity
 - **EDAM annotation guidelines** which are generically applicable when annotating the topic, operations, types of input and output data, and supported data formats of a tool
 - **attribute-specific guidelines** for individual software attributes defined in biotoolsSchema 3.0.0, laid out as they appear in the bio.tools Registration Interface
 - **tool type-specific guidelines** for individual types of tool
- **bio.tools API reference** describing the endpoints of the bio.tools RESTful API with example API calls
- **bio.tools API usage guide** describing how biotoolsSchema is implemented as a JSON schema in bio.tools, with detailed usage information and examples

And as works in progress:

- **bio.tools User Guide** to help users with practical use of the bio.tools Registration Interface
- **bio.tools Editors Guide** to help bio.tools Thematic Editors oversee coverage and quality of bio.tools in specific thematic areas.

2.2 biotoolsSchema documentation

biotoolsSchema docs are, where possible, embedded in the schema itself (the XSD file) and made available online:

- **general docs** such as background information, element (information field) descriptions, controlled vocabularies *etc.*
- **online technical specification** which is website describing the schema in exhaustive technical detail

2.3 EDAM documentation

EDAM docs include aims, scope, design principles, explanation of concepts, relations, hierarchy, contribution mechanisms, governance *etc.* In addition:

- **EDAM Editors Guide** of general best practice (technical and scientific) when modifying EDAM; adding or changing concepts, concept metadata, crosslinking, *etc.*
- **EDAM Developers Guide** for the technical processes of EDAM development; modifying EDAM files on GitHub, creation of releases, deprecation of concepts *etc.*

2.4 Tool Information Standard documentation

Tool Information Standard (described in D1.5) documentation describe the technical standard (attributes required at tiers of software metadata quality) and is cross-referenced to the Curators Guide and biotoolsSchema documentation.

3. Community build-up and user support

The agile, community-driven, user-centered approach first described in D1.1 and expanded in D1.2 continues to be applied to all aspects of the project, resulting in further

growth and activity of the community who are helping drive developments forward. The unique contributors (people with bio.tools user accounts) of content to the registry has grown from 537 (reported in D1.2) to 799⁴. As anticipated in D1.2, engagement with developers and support for end-users (see D1.7 report) have been prioritised over outreach events.

Events. WP1 personnel participated in 10 events in order to promote the community development of the portal. Details of all events are listed online⁵.

Open governance models described in D1.1 and revised in D1.2 has been further improved to encourage engagement:

- the 'registry-core' group has grown from 37 (in D1.2) to 38 members
- the EDAM governance model has been improved, following ideas laid out in D1.2:
 - the Steering group is reworked to be an Advisory Group (reflecting better the actual role of the people involved) with more focus on (and open to) adopters of EDAM
 - the EDAM Editors⁶ and bio.tools Thematic Editors⁷ (Section 8.3.1) have been consolidated and now constitute a single group of people with responsibility for oversight of scientific areas in bio.tools and EDAM

We plan to invite representatives of projects who are using, or seriously considering using EDAM, to join the Advisory Group; such as representatives from Galaxy, CWL, EBI OLS *etc.*

Sifterapp⁸ remains an efficient means for tracking issues (Table 3) for high-level task and project management, but with most technical discussion now encouraged via the relevant public GitHub trackers. Membership⁹ has increased to 121 members (was 111 in D1.2).

GitHub organisations for bio.tools¹⁰ (29 members, was 23 in D1.2) and EDAM¹¹ (14 members, was 12 in D1.2) remain the preferred method for public discussion and tracking fine-grained issues (Table 3)

Numerous other technical projects within the bio.tools and EDAM GitHub organisations, each with their own issue trackers (not reported here).

Tracker	URL	Issues (total)	Issues (open)	Issues (closed)
bio.tools	github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsregistry/issues	360	128	232

⁴ See D1.3 for further information.

⁵ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/events.html>

⁶ <http://edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributors.html#edam-editors>

⁷ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributors.html#registry-core-registry-editors>

⁸ <https://biotools.sifterapp.com>

⁹ This was erroneously reported in D1.1 as having 132 members

¹⁰ <https://github.com/bio-tools/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/edamontology/>

biotoolsSchem a	github.com/edamontology/edamontology/issues	103	15	88
EDAM	github.com/bio-tools/biotoolsschema/issues	369	76	293

Table 3. Issues tracked for project management and user support with technical aspects. There are numerous projects within the bio.tools and EDAM GitHub organisations not listed here.

JIRA remains in use for tracking low-level (implementation) software tasks.

Community mailing lists¹² remain low-traffic. Discussion is now encouraged primarily on GitHub (fully open, technical issues) or sifterapp (project management issues) instead. The registry-support list (for questions and help on bio.tools) gets regular traffic typically with a same day response.

bio.tools hangouts¹³ occur fortnightly or as required, and are focused on core curation and software development tasks to improve the quality of bio.tools content. They replace the general bio.tools hangouts (monthly) and curation-focused hangouts (weekly) reported in D1.2. Agenda and attendance are open and members of the Curation Taskforce (Section 3.2.3.1) regularly attend. EDAM¹⁴ hangouts occur *ad-hoc* primarily to drive EDAM releases.

3.1 Support for Thematic Editors

In D1.2 we outlined, as a scheme in its early stages, Thematic Editors who are registry-core¹⁵ members responsible for overseeing bio.tools and EDAM coverage and quality in specific thematic areas. The idea stemmed from an earlier attempt to organise such editors for EDAM. The scheme is already bearing fruit:

- development of EDAM in thematic areas (see D1.3)
 - Proteomics
 - Cheminformatics
 - Structural bioinformatics
 - Agricultural science
- systematic curation of proteomics analysis tools, yielding one publication in press and another in preparation (Section 8.4.1)

Our actions to develop the scheme further include:

- consolidating the earlier EDAM Editors group and Thematic Editors into a single group
- promoting the scheme for funding via the ELIXIR Tools Platform

As stated in D1.2, we anticipate the editorships will enable expanding accurate high-standard software annotations in bio.tools to most scientific topics in life science. Indeed, the idea was highlighted in the EXCELERATE midterm review as an excellent one. It is now clear, however, that Thematic Editors are only effective where backed up

¹² http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributors_guide.html#mailing-list

¹³ <https://tinyurl.com/btcontent>

¹⁴ <http://edamontologydocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/hangouts.html>

¹⁵ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/governance.html#registry-core>

by a student helper (see Section 8.3.2), thus we need to get new funding for the idea to scale.

3.2 bio.tools studentship scheme

In D1.2 we summarised how ELIXIR Denmark is supporting a scheme¹⁶ to enable students to work on curation-focussed mini-projects for bio.tools, to improve the registry, achieve outreach and support key partners. The projects and status:

- “Mining the Scientific Literature for and Annotating Proteomics Software using the EDAM ontology and biotoolsSchema”¹⁷
 - complete: contributed to outcomes including publications summarised in Section 8.4.1
- “Harvesting service descriptions for bio.tools using OpenAPI standards”¹⁸
 - complete: contributed to a pre-publication “*Automatic OpenAPI to Bio.tools Conversion*”¹⁹
 - more work is needed to bring the developments into production and funding was sought for this from the ELIXIR Tools Platform
- “Annotating software tools in a scientific context”²⁰
 - ongoing: four studentships actively driving bio.tools content quality improvements as per the Tool Information Standard²¹
- “Annotating software tools in domains of the Life Sciences”²²
 - ongoing: driving bio.tools and EDAM improvements for metabolomics

The schema will be extended - subject to funding - especially to support the emerging network of Thematic Editors (Section 8.3.1).

3.3 Curation Taskforce

The bio.tools curation taskforce, summarised in D1.2, has continued to meet on a regular basis to coordinate actions supporting high quality content growth towards comprehensive coverage of the prevalent bioinformatics tools. The output of this group is summarised in D1.3. We anticipate they will take a major role in supporting the emerging Thematic Editors (see below) - assuming this activity is funded.

4. Focused community support

4.1 Proteomics community

A collaboration with the proteomics community is working towards comprehensive coverage and high quality annotation of proteomics analysis tools, and the application of these data to workflow composition. The work has resulted in:

- Systematic expert curation of tools for proteomics data analysis, resulting in several hundred high quality new entries in bio.tools.

An article (summarised in D1.8) “*Automated workflow composition in mass*

¹⁶ <http://biotools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/studentships.html>

¹⁷ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/proteomics_software.pdf

¹⁸ <https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/openAPI.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1101/170274>

²⁰ https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/literature_integration.pdf

²¹ <https://bio-tools.github.io/Tool-Information-Standard/>

²² https://github.com/bio-tools/Studentships/blob/master/thematic_editing.pdf

spectrometry based proteomics” has been accepted for publication in *Bioinformatics* journal, and explores the value of tool semantic annotation for automated workflow composition (*i.e.* interoperability of tools).

- An article²³ (summarised in D1.8) “*Community curation of software tools as illustrated for mass spectrometry-based proteomics*” is in preparation for publication in *Briefings in Bioinformatics*. It illustrates the process from start to finish that Thematic Editors may follow for the curation of a corpus of tools in bio.tools.

4.2 Euro/Global-bioimaging

A collaboration with Euro/Global-bioimaging²⁴ via the NEUBIAS Cost Action²⁵ is working towards the systematic curation of bioimage analysis tools to a high standard, to ensure cross-infrastructure compatibility of software metadata, enabling easier data sharing and eventual surfacing of content from the Bio Image Information Index, BISE (<https://biii.eu>) in bio.tools. To these ends, the following work was done:

- collaborating with bioimage analysts and software developers at the 3 NEUBIAS tagathons run to date, to identify the required attributes and semantics
- mapping of the BISE information model to biotoolsSchema, followed by refactoring and extension of biotoolsSchema to support bioimaging requirements
- consolidation of existing tags used in BISE, followed by mapping the consolidated set to EDAM, and subsequent development of the EDAM-Bioimaging sub-ontology:
 - <http://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/EDAM-BIOIMAGING>
 - <https://github.com/edamontology/edam-bioimaging>
- application of the (refactored) attribute list and EDAM-Bioimaging to the 1188 software entries in BISE

Work is ongoing and future developments very much depend upon the funding environment; one option is the eventual migration of the BISE content to bio.tools and its maintenance there, another is the surfacing (as “locked” entries which cannot subsequently be edited in bio.tools) the content in bio.tools.

4.3 Technical communities

Collaborations with multiple technical communities and projects within and beyond ELIXIR are working towards the integration and interoperability of bio.tools with the broader resource landscape (Figure 2), to deliver practical benefits to those projects and their end-users broadly. The work, which was first summarised in D5.1 report, and is or will be described in detail in other future deliverable reports or publications in the scientific press includes:

- Support for EDAM in workbench and workflow environments. Specifically the Galaxy platform (see their article²⁶) now supports EDAM identifiers, as does Common Workflow Language, CWL²⁷. A prerequisite to this was the systematic

²³ <https://tinyurl.com/proteomics-tools>

²⁴ <http://www.eurobioimaging.eu/>

²⁵ <http://eubias.org/NEUBIAS/>

²⁶ <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/44/W1/W3/2499339>

²⁷ see https://www.commonwl.org/user_guide/16-file-formats/

mapping, and eventual coverage in EDAM, of all data formats known to Galaxy, that has been progressively tackled in EDAM releases 1.18 - 1.21. In due course this should user to not only find, but also use and connect tools deployed in those environments. This work will be taken forward at the forthcoming BioHackathon²⁸ in Paris.

- The mapping of EDAM to the tags or folksonomies used by various web resources, and subsequent extension of EDAM and (in some cases) revision of the annotation in those resources, bringing these things into harmony. Examples of this include the EBI Services collection²⁹, ExPASy³⁰, OLS³¹ and the Identifiers.org data collection³² (reported in D5.1), and also BioConductor³³, ms-utils.org³⁴, AppDB³⁵, BioCatalogue³⁶ and FAIRSharing³⁷. With more development, this will provide for a more cohesive end-user experience.
- The mapping of biotoolsSchema (the schema used by bio.tools) and EDAM to information schema developed for use in other technical or scientific contexts. The mapping is followed by revisions to bring the technical artefacts into better alignment. An example of this is the collaboration on development of BISE (Section 84.2). Another example is the compatibility of biotoolsSchema hence bio.tools with the BioSchema initiative³⁸, paving the way for mark-up of web pages, improving tool findability. There are many other examples including projects in the previous bullet.
- The mapping of EDAM to other, more specialised ontologies or vocabularies, including for example, the Data Science Education Ontology (DSEO³⁹), and emerging components of OpenMinTeD⁴⁰ infrastructure for text and data mining technologies. The mapping is followed by revision of EDAM and addition of ontology cross-references. This will, in due course, enable data sharing, e.g. of training resources collated by ELIXIR TeSS and annotated in terms from EDAM, and BigDataU⁴¹; a counterpart initiative in the US.

Excerpt from D5.1 report

²⁸ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/events/biohackathon-2018-paris>

²⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/services>

³⁰ <https://www.expasy.org/resources>

³¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/>

³² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/miriam/main/collections>

³³ <https://www.bioconductor.org/>

³⁴ <http://msutils.org/>

³⁵ <https://appdb.ebi.eu/>

³⁶ <https://www.biocatalogue.org/>

³⁷ <https://fairsharing.org/>

³⁸ <http://bioschemas.org/>

³⁹ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/DSEO>

⁴⁰ <https://guidelines.openminted.eu/about-openminted.html>

⁴¹ <https://bigdatau.ini.usc.edu/>

The EDAM ontology (<https://github.com/edamontology/edamontology/>) provides a controlled vocabulary for the systematic annotation of bioinformatics resources broadly, in terms for common topics, specific operations, types of data, data identifiers and data formats. bio.tools (<https://bio.tools>) provides a persistent reference to high-quality (curated and verified) “canonical” descriptions of unique tools, with information about their provision via online services and various downloadable artefacts. From an interoperability perspective, EDAM and bio.tools have numerous practical applications:

- Annotation of individual resources *e.g.* by inclusion of EDAM concept URIs or bio.tools IDs in resource metadata, thus providing a consistent and machine-readable scientific description that renders those resources more *findable* through whatever search mechanisms are deployed locally (application search box, Google search, results filtering *etc.*)
- Uptake of EDAM and bio.tools IDs across an ecosystem of resource collections (registries, catalogues, web portals *etc.*), thus providing a basis for crosslinking those collections and a more consistent nomenclature and end-user experience that renders those collections more *accessible*.
- Annotation of application software broadly (including tools, workflows and Web APIs) with specific operations, identifiers and data formats especially, thus providing a precise machine-readable statement of what a software does and what formats it consumes and generates, that renders these software more *interoperable*, regardless of whether this is exploited by a developer or another software agent.
- Annotations that provide for a richer and more consistent description of the provenance of data generated by specific tools and workflows, that will, in the longer term, render biological analysis pipelines more *reusable*.

Figure 2 Excerpt from D5.1 report putting bio.tools and EDAM in the interoperability context